

A PROOF OF THE CONTINUED FRACTION EXPANSION OF $e^{2/s}$

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Abstract

We give a proof of the continued fraction expansion of $e^{2/s}$, where $s \geq 3$ is an odd integer, by expressing the error between $e^{2/s}$ and its each convergent explicitly in terms of integrals.

1. Introduction

Let $\alpha = [a_0; a_1, a_2, \dots]$ denote the simple continued fraction expansion of a real α , where

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= a_0 + 1/\alpha_1, & a_0 &= \lfloor \alpha \rfloor, \\ \alpha_n &= a_n + 1/\alpha_{n+1}, & a_n &= \lfloor \alpha_n \rfloor \quad (n \geq 1). \end{aligned}$$

The n -th convergent of the continued fraction expansion is denoted by $p_n/q_n = [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_n]$, and p_n and q_n satisfy the recurrence relation:

$$\begin{aligned} p_n &= a_n p_{n-1} + p_{n-2} \quad (n \geq 0), & p_{-1} &= 1, & p_{-2} &= 0, \\ q_n &= a_n q_{n-1} + q_{n-2} \quad (n \geq 0), & q_{-1} &= 0, & q_{-2} &= 1. \end{aligned}$$

An irrational number α is well approximated by its n -th convergent p_n/q_n . In fact, for $n \geq 0$

$$\frac{1}{q_n(q_{n+1} + q_n)} < \left| \alpha - \frac{p_n}{q_n} \right| < \frac{1}{q_n q_{n+1}}$$

([4, p. 20]). Precisely speaking, by using the algorithm mentioned above, we can express ([1, Lemma 5.4]) the error as

$$\alpha - \frac{p_n}{q_n} = \frac{(-1)^n}{q_n(\alpha_{n+1}q_n + q_{n-1})}.$$

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Osler [5] gave a remarkable proof of the simple continued fraction

$$e^{1/s} = [1; \overline{(2k-1)s-1, 1}]_{k=1}^{\infty} \quad (s \geq 2)$$

by expressing this error explicitly in terms of integrals. Namely, when p_n/q_n is the n -th convergent of the continued fraction of $e^{1/s}$, he showed that for $n \geq 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{p_{3n}}{q_{3n}} - e^{1/s} &= -\frac{1}{q_{3n}} \int_0^1 \frac{x^n(x-1)^n}{s^{n+1}n!} e^{x/s} dx, \\ \frac{p_{3n+1}}{q_{3n+1}} - e^{1/s} &= \frac{1}{q_{3n+1}} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{n+1}(x-1)^n}{s^{n+1}n!} e^{x/s} dx \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\frac{p_{3n+2}}{q_{3n+2}} - e^{1/s} = \frac{1}{q_{3n+2}} \int_0^1 \frac{x^n(x-1)^{n+1}}{s^{n+1}n!} e^{x/s} dx.$$

This was the direct extension of the result given by Cohn [2] concerning e . A similar expression can be seen in [3] too.

It is known that the continued fraction expansion of $e^{2/s}$ is given by

$$e^{2/s} = [1; \overline{\frac{(6k-5)s-1}{2}, (12k-6)s, \frac{(6k-1)s-1}{2}, 1, 1}]_{k=1}^{\infty},$$

where $s > 1$ is odd (See [6], §32, (2)). We shall give another proof of the continued fraction expansion of $e^{2/s}$ by showing similar errors explicitly. For convenience, for $n \geq 0$ put

$$\begin{aligned} A_n &= \left(\frac{2}{s}\right)^{3n+1} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n}}{(3n)!} e^{2x/s} dx, \\ B_n &= \frac{2^{3n+1}}{s^{3n+2}} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}}{(3n+1)!} e^{2x/s} dx, \\ C_n &= \left(\frac{2}{s}\right)^{3n+3} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+2}}{(3n+2)!} e^{2x/s} dx, \\ D_n &= \left(\frac{2}{s}\right)^{3n+3} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{3n+3}(x-1)^{3n+2}}{(3n+2)!} e^{2x/s} dx, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$E_n = \left(\frac{2}{s}\right)^{3n+3} \int_0^1 \frac{x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+3}}{(3n+2)!} e^{2x/s} dx.$$

Then, our main theorem is stated as follows.

Theorem 1.1. *Let p_n/q_n be the n -th convergent of the continued fraction of $e^{2/s}$. Then, for $n \geq 0$*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{p_{5n}}{q_{5n}} - e^{2/s} &= -\frac{1}{q_{5n}}A_n, \\ \frac{p_{5n+1}}{q_{5n+1}} - e^{2/s} &= -\frac{1}{q_{5n+1}}B_n, \\ \frac{p_{5n+2}}{q_{5n+2}} - e^{2/s} &= -\frac{1}{q_{5n+2}}C_n, \\ \frac{p_{5n+3}}{q_{5n+3}} - e^{2/s} &= \frac{1}{q_{5n+3}}D_n, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\frac{p_{5n+4}}{q_{5n+4}} - e^{2/s} = \frac{1}{q_{5n+4}}E_n.$$

2. The Continued Fraction of $e^{2/s}$

The proof of the main theorem is based upon the following identities.

Lemma 2.1.

$$A_n = -E_{n-1} - D_{n-1}, \tag{2.1}$$

$$B_n = \frac{(6n + 1)s - 1}{2}A_n - E_{n-1}, \tag{2.2}$$

$$C_n = (12n + 6)sB_n + A_n, \tag{2.3}$$

$$D_n = -\frac{(6n + 5)s - 1}{2}C_n - B_n, \tag{2.4}$$

and

$$E_n = D_n - C_n. \tag{2.5}$$

These identities correspond with the desired relations:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{5n} &= p_{5n-1} + p_{5n-2}, & q_{5n} &= q_{5n-1} + q_{5n-2}, \\ p_{5n+1} &= \frac{(6n + 1)s - 1}{2}p_{5n} + p_{5n-1}, & q_{5n+1} &= \frac{(6n + 1)s - 1}{2}q_{5n} + q_{5n-1}, \\ p_{5n+2} &= (12n + 6)sp_{5n+1} + p_{5n}, & q_{5n+2} &= (12n + 6)sq_{5n+1} + q_{5n}, \\ p_{5n+3} &= \frac{(6n + 5)s - 1}{2}p_{5n+2} + p_{5n+1}, & q_{5n+3} &= \frac{(6n + 5)s - 1}{2}q_{5n+2} + q_{5n+1}, \\ p_{5n+4} &= p_{5n+3} + p_{5n+2}, & q_{5n+4} &= q_{5n+3} + q_{5n+2}. \end{aligned}$$

We shall prove Theorem 1.1 and Lemma 2.1 simultaneously.

Proof. When $n = 0$, the relations in Theorem 1.1 are true. Indeed,

$$A_0 = \frac{2}{s} \int_0^1 e^{2x/s} dx = e^{2/s} - 1 = q_0 e^{2/s} - p_0.$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_0 &= \frac{2}{s^2} \int_0^1 x(x-1)e^{2x/s} dx = \frac{1}{2s} [(2x^2 - 2(s+1)x + s^2 + s)e^{2x/s}]_0^1 \\ &= \frac{s-1}{2} e^{2/s} - \frac{s+1}{2} = q_1 e^{2/s} - p_1. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_0 &= \left(\frac{2}{s}\right)^3 \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 x^2(x-1)^2 e^{2x/s} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{s^2} [(2x^4 - 4(s+1)x^3 + 2(3s^2 + 3s + 1)x^2 \\ &\quad - 2s(3s^2 + 3s + 1)x + 3s^4 + 3s^3 + s^2)e^{2x/s}]_0^1 \\ &= (3s^2 - 3s + 1)e^{2/s} - (3s^2 + 3s + 1) = q_2 e^{2/s} - p_2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_0 &= \left(\frac{2}{s}\right)^3 \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 x^3(x-1)^2 e^{2x/s} dx \\ &= -\frac{1}{2s^2} [(4x^5 - (10s+8)x^4 + (20s^2 + 16s + 4)x^3 - (30s^3 + 24s^2 + 6s)x^2 \\ &\quad + (30s^4 + 24s^3 + 6s^2)x - (15s^5 + 12s^4 + 3s^3))e^{2x/s}]_0^1 \\ &= \frac{15s^3}{2} + 6s^2 + \frac{3s}{2} - \left(\frac{15s^3}{2} - 9s^2 + \frac{9s}{2} - 1\right) e^{2/s} = p_3 - q_3 e^{2/s}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &= \left(\frac{2}{s}\right)^3 \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 x^2(x-1)^3 e^{2x/s} dx \\ &= -\frac{1}{2s^2} [(4x^5 - (10s+12)x^4 + (20s^2 + 24s + 12)x^3 - (30s^3 + 36s^2 + 18s + 4)x^2 \\ &\quad + (30s^4 + 36s^3 + 18s^2 + 4s)x - (15s^5 + 18s^4 + 9s^3 + 2s^2))e^{2x/s}]_0^1 \\ &= \frac{15s^3}{2} + 9s^2 + \frac{9s}{2} + 1 - \left(\frac{15s^3}{2} - 6s^2 + \frac{3s}{2}\right) e^{2/s} = p_4 - q_4 e^{2/s}. \end{aligned}$$

Suppose that Theorem 1.1 is true up to some integer $n - 1 (\geq 0)$. Since

$$\frac{d}{dx} (x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n} e^{2x/s}) = 3nx^{3n-1}(x-1)^{3n} e^{2x/s} + 3nx^{3n}(x-1)^{3n-1} + \frac{2}{s} x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n} e^{2x/s},$$

by integrating from 0 to 1 we get (2.1). Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} p_{5n} - q_{5n} e^{2/s} &= (p_{5n-1} + p_{5n-2}) - (q_{5n-1} + q_{5n-2}) e^{2/s} \\ &= E_{n-1} + D_{n-1} = -A_n. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} (x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}) \\ &= 3nx^{3n-1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + (3n+1)x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} \\ &= -3nx^{3n-1}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \left(6n+1-\frac{2}{s}\right)x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} (x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}) \\ &= (3n+1)x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + (3n+1)x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} \\ &= 2(3n+1)x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} - (3n+1)x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}, \end{aligned}$$

by integrating from 0 to 1 and canceling the term of $x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s}$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{s}{2}(-3n) \int_0^1 x^{3n-1}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} dx + \frac{(6n+1)s-1}{2} \int_0^1 x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} dx \\ & \quad - \frac{1}{s(3n+1)} \int_0^1 x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} dx = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have (2.2). Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} p_{5n+1} - q_{5n+1}e^{2/s} &= \left(\frac{(6n+1)s-1}{2}p_{5n} + p_{5n-1}\right) - \left(\frac{(6n+1)s-1}{2}q_{5n} + q_{5n-1}\right)e^{2/s} \\ &= -\frac{(6n+1)s-1}{2}A_n + E_{n-1} = -B_n. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} (x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s}) \\ &= (3n+2)x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s} + (3n+2)x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s} \\ &= (6n+4)x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} - (3n+2)x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} (x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}) \\ &= (3n+2)x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + (3n+1)x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} \\ &= (6n+3)x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + (3n+1)x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} (x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}) \\ &= 2(3n+1)x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} - (3n+1)x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}. \end{aligned}$$

Integrating these three equations from 0 to 1 and canceling the terms of $x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}$ and $x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{2}{s}\right)^2 \int_0^1 x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s} dx \\ &= (12n+6)(3n+2) \int_0^1 x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} dx + (3n+2)(3n+1) \int_0^1 x^{3n}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have (2.3). Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} p_{5n+2} - q_{5n+2}e^{2/s} &= ((12n+6)sp_{5n+1} + p_{5n}) - ((12n+6)sq_{5n+1} + q_{5n})e^{2/s} \\ &= -(12n+6)sB_n - A_n = -C_n. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} (x^{3n+3}(x-1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s}) \\ &= (3n+3)x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s} + (3n+2)x^{3n+3}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+3}(x-1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} (x^{3n+3}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}) \\ &= (3n+3)x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + (3n+1)x^{3n+3}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+3}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} \\ &= \left(6n+4+\frac{2}{s}\right)x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + (3n+1)x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} (x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s}) \\ &= \left(6n+4-\frac{2}{s}\right)x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} - (3n+2)x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+3}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dx} (x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}) \\ &= (3n+2)x^{3n+1}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} + (3n+1)x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n}e^{2x/s} + \frac{2}{s}x^{3n+2}(x-1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}. \end{aligned}$$

Integrating these four equations from 0 to 1 and eliminating the terms of $x^{3n+3}(x - 1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}$, $x^{3n+2}(x - 1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s}$ and $x^{3n+2}(x - 1)^{3n}e^{2x/s}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{4}{s} \int_0^1 x^{3n+3}(x - 1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s} dx \\ &= - \left(12n + 10 - \frac{2}{s}\right) \int_0^1 x^{3n+2}(x - 1)^{3n+2}e^{2x/s} dx - (3n + 2) \int_0^1 x^{3n+1}(x - 1)^{3n+1}e^{2x/s} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have (2.4). Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} p_{5n+3} - q_{5n+3}e^{2/s} &= \left(\frac{(6n + 5)s - 1}{2}p_{5n+2} + p_{5n+1}\right) - \left(\frac{(6n + 5)s - 1}{2}q_{5n+2} + q_{5n+1}\right) e^{2/s} \\ &= -\frac{(6n + 5)s - 1}{2}C_n - B_n = D_n. \end{aligned}$$

Since $x^{3n+3}(x - 1)^{3n+2} - x^{3n+2}(x - 1)^{3n+2} = x^{3n+2}(x - 1)^{3n+3}$, we get $D_n - C_n = E_n$, which is (2.5). Hence,

$$p_{5n+4} - q_{5n+4}e^{2/s} = (p_{5n+3} + p_{5n+2}) - (q_{5n+3} + q_{5n+2})e^{2/s} = D_n - C_n = E_n.$$

□

3. The Continued Fraction of e^2

Let $\frac{p_n^*}{q_n^*}$ be the n^{th} convergent of the continued fraction of $e^2 = [7; \overline{3k - 1, 1, 1, 3k, 12k + 6}]_{k=1}^\infty$. Then, for $n \geq 0$ we have

$$\frac{p_n^*}{q_n^*} = \frac{p_{n+2}}{q_{n+2}},$$

where p_n/q_n is the n -th convergent of the continued fraction of $e^{2/s}$ mentioned above. Thus, by replacing p_n/q_n by p_{n-2}^*/q_{n-2}^* ($n \geq 2$), Theorem 1.1 with Lemma 2.1 holds for $s = 1$.

4. Additional Comments

Some results in our theorem can be derived directly from Osler’s results. By the relation for $i = 1, 2, \dots$

$$\left[\dots, 1, a_i - \frac{1}{2}, 1, \dots\right] = \left[\dots, 1, a_{3i-2}, 4a_{3i-1} + 2, a_{3i}, 1, \dots\right],$$

if we replace s by $s/2$ in the continued fraction $[1; \overline{(2k - 1)s - 1, 1, 1}]_{k=1}^\infty$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} [1; \overline{(2k - 1)s/2 - 1, 1, 1}]_{k=1}^\infty &= [1; ks - \frac{s + 1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}, 1, 1]_{k=1}^\infty \\ &= [1; \frac{(6k - 5)s - 1}{2}, (12k - 6)s, \frac{(6k - 1)s - 1}{2}, 1, 1]_{k=1}^\infty. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, if we replace s by $s/2$ and n by $3n$ in the Osler's integral for $p_{3n} - q_{3n}e^{1/s}$, we get our integral for $p_{5n} - q_{5n}e^{2/s}$. If we replace s by $s/2$ and n by $3n+2$ in the Osler's integral for $p_{3n+1} - q_{3n+1}e^{1/s}$, we get our integral for $p_{5n+3} - q_{5n+3}e^{2/s}$. If we replace s by $s/2$ and n by $3n+2$ in the Osler's integral for $p_{3n+2} - q_{3n+2}e^{1/s}$, we get our integral for $p_{5n+4} - q_{5n+4}e^{2/s}$.

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References

- [1] E. B. Burger, *Exploring the Number Jungle: A journey into Diophantine Analysis*, STML 8, American Mathematical Society, 2000.
- [2] H. Cohn, *A short proof of the simple continued fraction expansion of e* , Amer. Math. Monthly **113** (2006), 57–62.
- [3] C. S. Davis, *On some simple continued fractions connected with e* , J. London Math. Soc, **20** (1945), 194–198.
- [4] A. Ya. Khinchin, *Continued fractions*, Dover, New York, 1997.
- [5] T. Osler, *A proof of the continued fraction expansion of $e^{1/M}$* , Amer. Math. Monthly **113** (2006), 62–66.
- [6] O. Perron, *Die Lehre von den Kettenbrüchen*, Chelsea Publishing Company, New York, 1950.